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“LUSO” HYDROTHERMAL VENT FIELD

Expedition; 4th August 2018

(RV L'Atalante - IFREMER)

BLUE AZORES PROGRAM: EXPEDITION 2018 in collaboration with
TRANSECT program, CNRS- Université Pierre et Marie Curie (UPMC)

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1. Summary

Following the discovery of the new hydrothermal field “Luso” in the Azores during the scientific expedition “Oceano Azul” that took place in May and June, a follow up one day scientific sampling mission as part of the TRANSECT scientific campaign onboard the ship RV L’Atalante took place on August 4th. The mission was coordinated by Telmo Morato, chief scientist of the deep water exploration of the Oceano Azul expedition, in close collaboration with Nadine Le Bris, chief scientist of TRANSECT scientific campaign. The Portuguese team participating in the mission was composed of 4 scientists with different expertise in research areas of hydrothermal vents (e.g. geology, chemistry, ecology, microbiology) and the chief pilot of the Portuguese ROV Luso from EMEPC.

The main objective of the expedition was to collect sufficient information and samples for a proper description of the “LUSO” hydrothermal vent field area. Specifically, the mission aimed to collect information i) on the geological and geochemical (including chimneys and deposits/sediments) description of the area; ii) on the chemical composition of the vent fluids and gases, and on the environmental parameters that can help describing the area of influence of the vent; iii) on the biology and microbiology of the vent field; iv) the background fauna, mostly cold-water corals and sponges and v) to produce a photo-mosaic of the vent field. For this purpose a detailed dive plan based on the video footage collected during the first scientific mission in June identified three priority areas to be visited: (1) the main venting area with the largest identified vent chimney; (2) a secondary venting area composed of smaller active vent chimneys ; (3) an inactive vent field area.

All three areas were successfully visited and sampled with the ROV Victor during a 4.5 hours dive. Samples of vent fluids and gases (e.g. methane, sulphur, carbon dioxide, hydrogen, iron and other trace metals) were collected using the VICTOR fluid sampler (PEP, in syringes, 5l bags) and in situ measurements of physical-chemical variables were made with the ROV sensors (temperature, pH, Eh and H₂S) in vent orifices of the main and secondary venting areas and in the vicinity of surrounding fauna. In situ seawater filtration was further conducted for measurements of particulate organic matter in the different venting areas visited. Temperature in the large chimney was ~63° C and ~52° C in the secondary venting area. Preliminary onboard analysis of venting fluids indicates high levels of iron in all active areas sampled and low pH (pH~5). Observations of orange-red precipitates rimming the vent orifices and covering the chimneys suggest likely formation by the deposition of iron and manganese oxyhydroxides further suggesting the iron as a dominant element of this vent system. Geological samples were taken from the large chimney (including a portion of the inner and other surfaces of the chimney), a small active chimney in the secondary venting area, inactive chimneys, and pillow basalts in the vicinity of the vent field for mineralogical and geochemical characterization of the chimneys and determination of the age of the vent system.

Biological observations of the vents showed the presence of a gastropod (likely specialized vent fauna) in the external surface of the large main chimney. Other fauna observed on the external surface of the chimney included hydrarians and non-identified filamentous structures. These organisms and samples of the chimneys were collected for macro and micro-biological characterization of vent fauna. Samples of Cirripedia (cf. Balanomorpha, a suborder of the barnacles) and zoanthids observed in the close vicinity of the secondary venting area were also collected for taxonomical identification. Several crabs *Paromola cuvieri* carrying fragments of corals and other fauna were observed within the vent field and surrounding areas. One of these crabs carrying a fragment of the coral *Paragorgia johnsoni* observed was observed in the very close proximity of an active chimney.

A photo-mosaic of 20 by 20 meters was performed at the end of the dive for a fine-scale detailed characterization of the vent system.

2. Detailed description of the mission

Main objectives: The main objective of the expedition was to collect sufficient information and samples for a proper description of the “LUSO” hydrothermal vent field area (see scientific plan attached – Annex 1). Specifically, the mission aimed to collect information i) on the geological and geochemical (including chimneys and deposits/sediments) description of the area; ii) on the chemical composition of the vent fluids and gases, and on the environmental parameters that can help describing the area of influence of the vent; iii) on the biology and microbiology on the vent field; iv) the background fauna, mostly cold-water corals and sponges and v) to produce a photo-mosaic of the vent field. For this purpose a detailed dive plan based on the video footage collected during the first scientific mission in June identified three priority areas to be visited (see Dive plan as annex 2, Fig 1): (1) the main venting area with the largest identified vent chimney (Pos 1); (2) a secondary venting area composed of smaller active vent chimneys (Pos 2); (3) an inactive vent field area where barite vent chimneys were visible (Pos 3).

Fig. 1. Location of the 3 sites sampled within the *Luso* hydrothermal vent field (Pos1, Pos2 and Pos3) with the ROV Victor during the Luso expedition.

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Dive log summary

08:30 am. Start dive. Submerge ROV Victor just a few metres south of the location of the hydrothermal vents discovered during the Blue Azores Expedition in June 2018.

08:30 am. Reach the bottom at 613 m depth. . Seafloor covered by basalt boulders some with ropy texture overlain predominantly by the gorgonian species *Corallium johnsoni* and the anthozoan *Anthomastus* cf. *agaricus* (Fig. 2). A deep-sea shark, possibly belonging to the species *Dalatias licha*, was also observed.

08:37 am. Pillow lavas

Fig. 2. Images of the area where the ROV reached the seabed, characterized by the presence of colonies of the species *Corallium johnsoni* (close up on top right). Loose, fresh volcanic clasts cover the seafloor surface and overlain basaltic flows suggest recent volcanic activity.

08:44 am. Moving towards the hydrothermal vent Luso, seafloor substrate exhibits ochre colours.

Fig. 3. Aspect of the substrate when approaching the hydrothermal vent, which changed from dark to a reddish colour.

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08:48 am. Arrival at sampling site 1 ($38^{\circ} 59.0329$ N, $29^{\circ} 50.0651$ W). The largest hydrothermal orifice (Boca Grande) was rapidly detected. The ROV positioned itself immediately in front of the orifice to collect samples of fluids and gases (e.g. methane, sulphur, iron and other trace metals) and perform in situ measurements of physical-chemical variables with the ROV sensors (temperature, O_2 , pH, iron, sulphide). Observations of a gastropod, hydrarians and non-identified filamentous structures in the external surface of the chimney. Slurp of this fauna using ROV slurp gun. Collection of a part of the vent chimney using ROV arm for the geological and biological (macro and micro-biology) characterization of the vents.

Fig. 4. Images of the sampling events performed at the largest orifice of the Luso hydrothermal vent site (Boca Grande). Top left: collection of water. Top right: measure of temperature, dissolved oxygen and pH. Bottom left: Slurp gun to collect samples to characterize the associated biological community. Bottom right: collection of a piece of the vent with ROV arm for microbiological analysis and geological characterization.

10:18 am. Arrival at sampling site 2 ($38^{\circ}59.0394$ N, $29^{\circ} 50.0679$ W). Smaller vent chimneys were identified and sampled following the same procedure applied in sampling site 1. Crab *Paromola cuvieri* carrying fragments of *Paragorgia johnsoni* observed next to an active chimney.

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Fig. 5. Images of the sampling events performed at Sampling site 2. Top left: measure of temperature, dissolved oxygen and pH. Top right: measure of temperature. Bottom left: Slurp gun to collect samples to characterize the associated biological community. Bottom right: collection of a piece of the vent for microbiological analysis and geological characterization. Notice the crab *Paromola cuvieri* carrying a fragment of the coral *Paragorgia jonhsoni* in the close vicinity of the vent chimney sampled.

11:14 am. Arrival at sampling site 3 (38° 59.03327 N 29° 50.0582938 W). Collection of samples of inactive chimneys for a thorough geological characterization. Sponges and ascidians and small white spots (micro-gastropods?) observed on the external surfaces of the vent chimneys. No time for water sampling.

Fig. 6. Images of the samples collected in the area of inactive chimneys.

12:00 Return to sampling site 2, where an aggregation of Cirripedia was observed, together with zoanthids that could not be identified directly from the video images. Samples of both species were collected.

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Fig. 7. Images of the samples taken from the cirriped aggregation.

12:27 pm. Once all samples were collected, the ROV Victor started the process of taking a series of still pictures using the down-facing camera with the objective of generating a photomosaic that will allow for a very detailed characterization of the area. Due to time limitations, the photomosaic was circumscribed to the limits of the 20 by 20 meters box illustrated in Figure 1.

12:57 pm Just after the photomosaic procedure was completed, the ROV moved away from the area of influence of the vents, towards the south ($38^{\circ} 59.0036$ N $29^{\circ} 50.0697$ W) and fragments of pillow basalts were collected.

Fig. 8. Sampling of two rocks in the area furthest away from the vents that was visited.

01:06 pm. End dive.

2.2 Chemical composition of the vent fluids and gases

In situ measurement of temperature, pH, Eh and H_2S were performed at the outflow of two chimneys and in the vicinity of surrounding fauna (vent fauna and Cirripedia). Vent fluids, gases and the water surrounding biological assemblages were sampled using the VICTOR fluid sampler (PEP, in syringes, 5l bags with in situ filtration); O_2 , pH and acid volatile sulphide (i.e. including dissolvable FeS) were measured on board by the LECOB team. Additional collaborations by members of the TRANSECT project team will analyse total iron (Mustafa Yücel, METU) and metals on shore (Mustafa Yücel, METU) and gases (CO_2 , CH_4 , H_2) (Cédric Boulart, CNRS). Samples are currently being processed and results will be shared within the next couple of months. Preliminary onboard analysis of venting fluids indicates high levels of iron in all active areas sampled and low pH (pH~5). Temperature in the large chimney was $\sim 63^{\circ}C$ and $\sim 52^{\circ}C$ in the secondary venting area.

In situ seawater filtration and seawater sample collection were performed for inorganic nutrient determination and for both microbial and chemical analyses of particulate material. Filters and sea water samples are deposited at IMAR for further analyses.

2.3 Geology e geochemistry

A total of seven geological samples were taken from the large chimney (including a portion of the inner and other surfaces of the chimney), a small active chimney in the secondary venting area, inactive chimneys and pillow basalts in the vicinity of the vent field (Table 1). Preliminary petrographic descriptions of the samples are presented in Annex 3. Petrochemical and geochemical analyses will be conducted in the laboratory by Drs Filipa Marques (UiB) and Ágata Dias (USJ).

Table 1- Geological samples collected during the Luso expedition.

Sampling site	Latitude (N)	Longitude (W)	Depth (m)	Code	Sample description	Preservation method
Sampling site 1	38° 59.0329	29° 50.0651	566	R1	Sample of the large active chimney	Dry
Sampling site 2	38°59.0394	29° 50.0679	568	R2	Sample of the small active chimney	Dry
Sampling site 3	38° 59.03327	29° 50.05829		R3	Sample of inactive vents	Dry
Sampling site outside vent field	38° 59.0036	29° 50.0697		R5	Pillow basalts	Dry
				R6	Pillow basalts	Dry
				R7	Pillow basalts	Dry

2.4 Biology and microbiology of the vent field

Sixteen biological samples were collected from the 3 main areas identified in Figure 1. Samples were preserved in ethanol, formol or frozen for subsequent taxonomical identification, isotopic and microbiology studies (Table 2). These samples are deposited at the biological reference collection (COLETA) at University of Azores.

Tabela 2- Biological samples collected during the Luso expedition.

Sampling site	Latitude (N)	Long. (W)	Depth (m)	Code	Sample description	Preservation method
Sampling site 1	38° 59.0329	29° 50.0651	566	S1-1	Gastropod on the large chimney	<i>Ethanol 96%</i>
				S2-1	Small filamentous structures in the external surface of the large chimney	<i>Ethanol 96%</i>
					Portion of the outer side of the large chimney for microbial characterization	Frozen at – 80 C
				R1-M1	Portion of the outer side of the large chimney for microbial characterization	Frozen at – 80 C
					Portion of the inner side of the large chimney for microbial characterization	Frozen at – 80 C
				R1-M2	Portion of the inner side of the large chimney for microbial characterization	Frozen at – 80 C
				R1-M3	Fine sediments and biological material left	<i>Ethanol 96%</i>
				BB1-B1		

					in the BB where R1 was stored	
Sampling site 2					Small filamentous structures in the small chimney	
	38°59.0394	29° 50.0679	568	S3	Hermit crab and hydrarians in the small chimney	
				S4	Portion of the small chimney for microbial characterization	Frozen at – 80 C
				R2-M1	Portion of the small chimney for microbial characterization	Frozen at – 80 C
				R2- M2	Fine sediments and biological material left	Ethanol 96%
				BB2–B1, B2, B3	in the BB where R2 was stored	
Sampling site 3					Fauna associated to inactive vents	Ethanol 96%
	38° 59.03327	29° 50.05829		R3 –B1	Cirripeds and zoanths	Ethanol 96%
Sampling site 2 (Cirripedia aggregation)	38°59.0394	29° 50.0679	570	BB3- B1-1	Cirripeds and zoanths	Formol 4%
				BB3- B1-2	Cirripeds	Frozen -20 C
				BB3- B1-3	Empty shells of cirripeds	Ethanol 96%
Sampling site outside vent field	38° 59.0036	29° 50.0697		BB3-B2	Fauna associated to pillow basalts	Ethanol 96%
				R5-B1	Fauna associated to pillow basalts	Ethanol 96%
				R6 –B1	Fauna associated to pillow basalts	Ethanol 96%
				R7-B1	Fauna associated to pillow basalts	Ethanol 96%

Preliminary conclusions:

- The E slope of the seamount is characterized by multiple volcanic flows with different degrees of seafloor weathering;
- Hydrothermal chimneys appear to have a fault-fracture controlled distribution, ENE-WSW with evidence for very recent volcanic activity due to the presence of fresh hyaloclastite on the seabed;
- Hydrothermal fluids venting from the chimneys are clear, no bubbling is visible, have low temperature (~60° C) and low pH (pH~5) suggesting that these vents are integrated in a low-temperature hydrothermal system;
- Iron appears to be the dominant element in the vent fluids. Thus, the vent system may have an important role as a source of iron, an often limiting micro-nutrient to surrounding seawater, increasing primary productivity and associated food chain. The diverse coral gardens observed in the vicinity of the vent system may depend on this increased primary productivity. Further, this iron can bind to organic particles in the water column and disperse widely potentially fertilizing large areas of the ocean.
- Typical vent macrofauna (e.g. mytilids and alvinocaridid shrimp) were not observed, but a non-identified gastropod, hydrarians, anthozoans and a peculiar community of deep water reddish-yellowish Cirripedia (cf. Balanomorpha, a suborder of the barnacles) were reported;

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- The extensive iron-oxyhydroxide clay fraction material cover within the venting area may harbor diverse bacterial communities;
- The apparent absence of methane and sulphur (toxic elements) in the vent fluids, together with low pH and temperature nature of the vent system, may constitute a potential site for establishing a natural laboratory for conducting long-term studies on the effects of ocean acidification and warming on benthic communities in the deep-sea. All existing natural laboratories are located in shallow waters (< 30 m depth).

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